

THE EFFECT OF MACRO ECONOMIC FACTOR ON STOCK RETURN OF STATE-OWNED ENTERPRISES (BUMN) LISTED ON THE INDONESIA STOCK EXCHANGE

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Abstract

This contemplate directs to influence the chain reaction of macroeconomic constituents on inventory turn back of state-owned undertakings (BUMN) catalogued on the Indonesia inventory Exchange. The investigator put into practice a descriptive decimal approach. Determination value t count (1. 101086) distinct possibility Слово которое было заменено: probability вариантызамен: distinct possibility expectation likelihood likeliness chances chance odds expenditure of 0. 2765 >0. 05 (α) which have in mind that statistically possibility 1 is rejected, signification that ostentatiousness has no chain reaction on inventory turn back in state-owned fellowships on the Indonesia inventory Exchange. Determination value t count (9. 759502) >t table (2010) with a distinct possibility expenditure of 0. 0000 <0. 05 (α) which have in mind that statistically possibility 2 is accepted, signification that interestingness reprimands influence inventory turn back in state-owned fellowships on the Indonesia inventory Exchange. Determination value t count (60. 94152) >t table (1. 67722) with a distinct possibility expenditure of 0. 0000 <0. 05 (α) which have in mind that statistically possibility 3 is accepted, signification that the Rupiah substitution proportion has an chain reaction on inventory turn back in BUMN fellowships on the Indonesia inventory Exchange. Determination value F count (-15. 66667) distinct possibility Слово которое было заменено: probability вариантызамен: distinct possibility expectation likelihood likeliness chances chance odds expenditure of 1. 0000 >0. 05 (α) which have in mind that possibility 4 is rejected, signification that Inflation, interestingness Rates, Rupiah substitution reprimands chalk up no contemporaneous chain reaction on inventory turn back in BUMN fellowships on the Indonesia inventory Exchange.

Keywords: Macro Economic Factor and State-Owned Enterprises (BUMN) Stock Returns.

INTRODUCTION

The majuscule marketplace cannot be distributed from environmental influences. substitutions in the macroeconomic environment, much as substitutions in interestingness rates, furthermore influence expenditure fluctuations variations and trading publication in the majuscule market. marketplace businesslike majuscule is a majuscule marketplace whose participation expenditures speedily full be resonant each available contemporary and substantial information, These macroeconomics accommodate overweight internal product, unemployment, inflation, interestingness rates, and budget deficits. Investors be required to remuneration consideration to the company's international and intragroup constituents

accompanying to his determination to invest in or convey title a attraction and stock. international constituents that pauperization to be advised are macroeconomic constituents consisting of inflation, interestingness reprimands and the rupiah substitution rate, patch the company's intragroup constituents that pauperization to be advised are accompanying to asset settlements and corporation supporting decisions. Macroeconomic constituents are constituents elsewhere the corporation that influence the aggrandizement or diminution in corporation performance. repositioning of macroeconomic constituents buoy be euphemistic pre-owned to prognosticate inventory expenditure movements, on the other hand each investigator put into practice contradistinctive macroeconomic constituents thanks to thither is no consensus on which macroeconomic constituents influence inventory prices. (Wulandari, 2015). severals researchers be credulous that many macroeconomic variables, much as high-pitched interestingness rates, high-pitched ostentatiousness reprimands and high-pitched substitution proportion fluctuations variations consideration fellowships to acquaintance pecuniary tribulations which buoy abbreviate their pecuniary bringing off resulting in a diminution in corporation expenditure and inventory turn back.

ReturnShares By(Fahmi, 2013), is as come after “Stock appearance is the advantage an investor look forward in closer on the proportion of resources that chalk up been placed. apprehensions characterize something that buoy come to pass elsewhere of what is expected. According to(Jogiyanto, 2014), inventory turn back are as come after “Stock appearance is the determination obtained from inventory investment. turn back buoy be in the configuration of accomplished turn back that chalk up occurred or anticipated turn back that chalk up not all the more occurred on the other hand which are anticipated to eventualize in the future.

Return Stock is a cocksureness expenditure of the corporation that testament come across a cocksureness carved figure to the company. In this manner the corporation is advised competitor and challenges to struggle and buoy accommodate an impression of optimism in underdeveloped the company. In the meantime contradiction inventory turn back buoy abbreviate the company's carved figure in the eyeballs of investors, in consequence in achieving its billy-goats the corporation be in want of to come around corporation performance. Corporation expenditure is far-reaching for the company. The possessors of the corporation deprivation a high-pitched corporation expenditure thanks to it testament aggrandizement the successfulness of shareholders. State-Owned undertakings (BUMN) are fellowships operational underneath the protections of the Asian government.

The proportion of appearance (return) of the company's apportionments catalogued on the marketplace majuscule (stock market) throw back the corporation or patronage protest chalk up the qualification to carry forward to constitute higher resource or mark down resource which jeopardizes losing self-confidence and apportionments of investors. This applies to inventory turn back of fellowships catalogued on the Indonesia inventory substitution (IDX) acquaintances inconsistent aggrandizement annually year, including State-Owned undertakings (BUMN) which accomplished fluctuations variations for the amplitude 2016 to 2020 with a moving down trend.

The undermentioned is the exploitation of the inventory turn back of the State-Owned undertakings (BUMN) which buoy be seen from the tabularise 1. 1 follows.

Table 1.1: Development of State-Owned Enterprise Stock Returns on the IDX in 2017-2021

No	Company name	Year				
		2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
1	AdhiKarya (Persero) Tbk	0.02	0.31	0.48	0.44	0.08
2	Aneka Tambang (Persero) Tbk	0.11	0.04	0.20	0.15	0.12
3	Bank Negara Indonesia Tbk	0.26	0.01	0.03	0.08	0.23
4	Bank Rakyat Indonesia (Persero) Tbk	0.30	0.29	0.05	0.04	0.33
5	Bank Mandiri (Persero) Tbk	0.18	0.04	0.20	0.03	0.19
6	JasaMarga (Persero) Tbk	0.24	0.23	0.14	0.13	0.09
7	Semen Indonesia (Persero) Tbk	0.05	0.21	0.18	0.20	0.14
8	WijayaKarya (Persero) Tbk	0.09	0.10	0.18	0.07	0.21
9	Bank BTN, Tbk	0.22	0.23	0.33	0.42	0.41
10	Kimia Farma, Tbk	0.11	0.14	0.19	0.22	0.25
11	State Gas Company, Tbk	0.33	0.21	0.27	0.33	0.28
12	Bukit Asam, Tbk	0.22	0.31	0.39	0.11	0.24
13	Housing Development, Tbk	0.14	0.35	0.26	0.22	0.26
14	Semen Baturaja, Tbk	0.20	0.23	0.29	0.21	0.18
15	Timah, Tbk	0.28	0.28	0.26	0.28	0.31
16	Telkom, Tbk	0.33	0.34	0.31	0.29	0.26
17	Waskita Karya, Tbk	0.22	0.27	0.25	0.25	0.20

Sources: IDX, Yahoo Finance, stocks (2021)

Supported on tabularise 1. 1, it buoy be seen that the occurrence of appearance fluctuations variations with a moving down direction for the amplitude 2016 to 2020. This consideration interprets that the corporation has not been best in generating expenditure to aggrandizement corporation performance. The lastest intermediate diminutive occurred in 2013 reached the 1.00% point, it buoy be aforementioned that in that amplitude the BUMN did not constitute advantage (return). This condition buoy influence the shareholders (investors) who deprivation to purchase the company. The diminutive that take place has an consequence on asset settlements and investor game plan if the company's patronage movements are disrupted it testament consideration rock-bottom capital, incorporated resource and sovereign state revenue. configuration This is surely a disputed point that be required to be addressed at the moment company.

Another factor that lay hold of inventory turn back from macroeconomics is inflation, supported on preceding evaluation conducted by(Rossy, 2018) state of affairs that the delimitation of ostentatiousness as come after ostentatiousness is a uninterrupted

aggrandizement in oecumenical expenditures continuously. An aggrandizement in the expenditure of individual or cardinal artifacts is not titled inflation, unless it outstretches to a comprehensive belonging of the expenditure of over-the-counter goods. Makin The higher the expenditure increase, the mark down the expenditure of money. in the meantime deposit Indonesia fix up with provision the delimitation of Inflation, videlicet the oecumenical and uninterrupted aggrandizement in prices. An aggrandizement in individual or cardinal artifacts unaccompanied cannot be titled ostentatiousness unless the aggrandizement outstretches (or consequences in an aggrandizement in the price) of over-the-counter goods.

Ostentatiousness is furthermore a disputed point that every conservation faces. The proportion to which this disputed point is deficient varies from once to another, and furthermore from individual sovereign state to another. The ostentatiousness proportion is the proportion aggrandizement in expenditures in a precondition year, unremarkably euphemistic pre-owned as a measurement to establish how deficient the economical predicaments are. In a expeditiously underdeveloped economy, subordinate ostentatiousness is recognized as crawling inflation, that is, ostentatiousness of few than one-tenth a year. Recurrently the ostentatiousness is bounteous contemplative or severe, videlicet ostentatiousness who's commensurate reaches out hold out in the sky hundred pct a year. In intervals of war conflict or governmental instability, ostentatiousness buoy reach a higher commensurate which is titled hyperinflation.

Table 1.2: Inflation Data

Tanggal	Data Inflasi
Juli 2021	1.52 %
Juni 2021	1.33 %
Mei 2021	1.68 %
April 2021	1.42 %
Maret 2021	1.37 %
Februari 2021	1.38 %
Januari 2021	1.55 %
Desember 2020	1.68 %
November 2020	1.59 %
Oktober 2020	1.44 %

Source: Central Bank of the Republic of Indonesia (2020-2021)

Another factor that lay hold of inventory turn back from the macro conservation is the interestingness rate, supported on preceding evaluation conducted by (Wulandari, 2015) "The interestingness proportion is the expenditure that be required to be paying for the majuscule and the majuscule acquires provided. In over-the-counter brief conversation the interestingness proportion is the expenditure that be required to be paying to general public who venture their majuscule in the configuration of majuscule or business. The interestingness proportion is individual pointer in deciding if someone testament venture or save. The interestingness proportion is verbalized as a proportion of paramount per constituent of time. interestingness is a measurement of the expenditure of processes euphemistic pre-owned by debtors that be required to be paying to creditors. By comparing the commensurate of advantage and jeopardy in the majuscule marketplace with the interestingness reprimands offered by the pecuniary sector, investors buoy decide which configuration of asset is accomplished to constitute best returns.

Interestingness proportion (BI rate), is the procedure interestingness proportion that throw back the pecuniary procedure department or department establish by deposit Indonesia and proclaimed to the public. generally, deposit Indonesia testament aggrandizement the BI proportion if looked toward ostentatiousness is estimated to be superior to the pre-established target, on the over-the-counter hand, deposit Indonesia testament mark down the BI proportion if looked toward ostentatiousness is estimated to be farther down the pre-established target. (Indonesia, 2015). Theoretically the interestingness proportion (BI rate) buoy influence the commensurate of requirement for credit, when interestingness reprimands are high rise the requirement for accomplishment testament decrease. Conversely, when interestingness reprimands dip circle the requirement for accomplishment testament increase, on the other hand absolutely this conception is not in conformation with what is contemporary in the banking industry.

Indonesia's reference interestingness proportion is according at 3. 50% pa in 2021-04. This digital audiotape stays behind compared to the preceding 3. 50% pay for 2021-03. Indonesia's reference interestingness proportion collection is updated monthly, with an intermediate of 5. 00 % pas from 2015-06 to 2021-04, with 71 observations. These collections affect an accomplishment high-pitched of 6. 25% pa in 2015-12 and an accomplishment little of 3. 50% pa in 2021-04. Indonesia's reference interestingness proportion collections stays behind indefatigable at CEIC and is according by deposit of Indonesia.

Figure 1.2: Reference Interest Rate

Source : Bank Of Indonesia (2020-2021)

In the Asian economy, the publication of interestingness reprimands (domestic) is an extremely far-reaching macro indicator. This indicator has constituents that consideration and chalk up an extremely terrible contradiction consequence to the conservation i.e. addressed immediately. Our conservation has sophistication of immersion of high-pitched interestingness rates. In Indonesia, interestingness reprimands are not dispassionate as a pointer of the expenditure of funds, on the other hand at the corresponding continuance and pointer people's appreciation for time.

Another factor that lay hold of inventory turn back from the macro conservation is the rupiah substitution rate, supported on preceding evaluation conducted by (Suryadie, Fajar Siddiq, 2017) the rupiah substitution proportion is the expenditure of the rupiah for over-the-counter countries' currencies. So, the rupiah substitution proportion is the expenditure of individual rupiah up-to-dateness which is translated into another country's currency. The substitution proportion is individual of the virtually far-reaching expenditures in an administer conservation precondition much a comprehensive consequence on the contemporary explanation symmetricalness and over-the-counter macroeconomic variables". The substitution proportion is the expenditure of a up-to-dateness for a strange currency, how all the more the internal up-to-dateness is precious by a strange currency, the substitution proportion is a extremely far-reaching expenditure in the conservation

And the repositioning of a country's up-to-dateness substitution proportion buoy furthermore is pretentious surrounded by others by the commerce balance, interestingness reprimands and inflation. Fundamental symmetricalness commerce balance, a country's commerce symmetricalness has in it each above from the marketing and invests in of artifacts and services.

The commerce symmetricalness or furthermore recognized as the export-import symmetricalness is the differentiation between the expenditure of a country's exports and introduces on top of a trustworthy period, measurable victimisation the predominant currency. A country's commerce symmetricalness is titled a deficiency if the sovereign state recompenses bounteous to its trading coordinate nations than the above obtained from trading coordinate countries, in over-the-counter brief conversation introduces are in a superior way than exports, which occasions the substitution proportion of the country's up-to-dateness to weaken. The diametrically opposed condition is titled a surplus, which occasions the substitution proportion of the country's up-to-dateness to reinforce for its coordinate country.

Figure 1.3: Price Rupiah Exchange Rate

Nilai Tukar Mata Uang Asing Terhadap Rupiah

CSV Excel PDF

Tahun	USD	JPY	DEM	NLG	GBP	FRH	CHF	SGD	MYR	HKD	A
2021	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Januari	14,084.00	13,482.04	0.00	0.00	19,310.59	0.00	15,837.20	10,584.31	3,475.40	1,816.70	10,7
Februari	14,229.00	13,429.29	0.00	0.00	19,947.66	0.00	15,733.96	10,733.62	3,513.78	1,834.92	11,1
Maret	14,572.00	13,166.48	0.00	0.00	20,003.72	0.00	15,447.08	10,818.12	3,508.38	1,874.18	11,0
April	14,468.00	13,276.44	0.00	0.00	20,170.56	0.00	15,893.68	10,906.08	3,526.64	1,863.84	11,2
Mei	14,310.00	13,025.08	0.00	0.00	20,320.93	0.00	15,934.53	10,814.70	3,461.55	1,843.78	11,0
Juni	14,496.00	13,105.51	0.00	0.00	20,061.02	0.00	15,737.72	10,781.31	3,492.60	1,867.24	10,9

Source: [statistic.kemendag.go.id/exchange-rates\(2020-2021\)](http://statistic.kemendag.go.id/exchange-rates(2020-2021))

Each sovereign state always perseveres in the substitution proportion of the country's internal up-to-dateness in an unchanging sovereign state for strange substitution rates. The substitution proportion changelessness is requisite to constitute contributive weathers for patronage activities. With contributive weathers for patronage activities, it is anticipated to aggrandizement the economical aggrandizement of a sovereign state.

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Stock returns

(Verawati, 2014) According to "stock turn back are unquestionably proportionate to risk, signification that the in a superior way the jeopardy borne by shareholders, the in a superior way the profits gross and vice versa". Delimitation of appearance according to (Supramono, 2014) Return is the advantage that obtained by companies, individuals and originations from the consequences of asset procedures what he did. Inventory turn back is the proportion of appearance for characteristic inventory and is a expenditure booking clerk conventional as a determination of ownership of a participation at the continuance of original investment.

2.2 Inflation

Ostentatiousness is a cognitive semantics of increasing the predominant expenditures in economy (Sukirno, 2015). In the same according to (Putong, 2013), which state of affairs that: "Inflation is the ecumenical aggrandizement in artifact expenditures which" This is caused by the synchronization between the artifact procurement transaction announcement (production, pricing, publication almighty dollar etc.) with the commensurate of resource owned by the community. Thither is furthermore the delimitation of ostentatiousness according to (Gilarso, 2013) is an increase general price, which staunches from the interruption of the symmetricalness between the menstruation of almighty dollar and the menstruation of goods.

2.3 Interest Rate

Interestingness proportion according to (Boediono, 2014) is "the expenditure of victimisation loanable funds. The interestingness proportion is individual pointer in deciding if someone testament venture or save. Interestingness proportion according to (Sunariyah, 2014) is the "price of the loan. The interestingness proportion is verbalized as a proportion of paramount per constituent of time. Interestingness is a measurement of the expenditure of processes euphemistic pre-owned by debtors that be required to be paying to creditors.

2.4 Rupiah exchange rate

Delimitation of Rupiah substitution proportion according to (Adiningsih, 2017) is as come after "The Rupiah substitution proportion is the expenditure of the rupiah for the currencies of over-the-counter countries". Delimitation of Rupiah substitution proportion according to (Ismanthono, 2015) is as the following: "The rupiah substitution proportion is the substitution proportion between individual up-to-dateness and another which is magisterial between the purchasing proportion (bid/buying rate) and the marketing proportion (offer/selling rate)".

RESEARCH METHOD

This classification of evaluation is interpretative research, according to (Supriyanto, 2013) explanatory evaluation is to evaluation the possibility between the hypothesized variables. therein contemplate thither is a possibility that testament be well-tried for truth. The possibility give an account of the communication between cardinal variables, to treasure trove elsewhere if a changeable is related or not with over-the-counter variables, or if the changeable is caused or influenced or not by over-the-counter variables. therein glance at the investigator tries to account for the chain reaction of macro economical constituents on inventory turn back of state-owned undertakings (BUMN) catalogued on the Indonesia inventory Exchange.

Less important collections is collections obtained or self-collected by general public conducting evaluation from existing sources (Sugiyono, 2016). This collections is euphemistic pre-owned to facilitate influential enlightenment that has been obtained, videlicet from the publishing of pecuniary declarations publicized nailed down the website [www. Id, report](http://www.Id.report)

macroeconomic pointers (inflation, interestingness reprimands and substitution rates) publicized by www...

Undergrounds of collections solicitation by victimisation of the disposition of creative writings and documentation methods. The collection method, videlicet by deed collections from recitation and studying backhand fountain-heads or indications accompanying to the predicaments discussed. Documentation method, videlicet by obtaining collections from certificates in the configuration of descriptions on Inflation, interestingness Rates, Rupiah substitution reprimands and inventory Returns. individual of the examinations that be required to be passed in aggregate one-dimensional retrogression psychoanalysis is the graeco-roman presumptuousness test. (Ghozali, 2011) said that the graeco-roman presumptuousness evaluation was carried elsewhere so that the aggregate one-dimensional retrogression representation met the disconsolate (Based one-dimensional nonpartisan Estimator) criteria. The analytic disposition euphemistic pre-owned is a aggregate one-dimensional retrogression representation to influence the progression of the communication between the self-governing and drug-addicted variables if each changeable is unquestionably and negatively related the equation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The classification of collections euphemistic pre-owned in this contemplate is less important collections in the configuration of venire collections for an amplitude of 3 second childhood from 2018-2020. The determination of the contemplate was to treasure trove elsewhere if the self-governing variables had a chain reaction on the drug-addicted changeable.

4.1 Common Effect Model

Table 4.1: Common Effect Model Test Results

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.028577	0.010992	2.599792	0.0124
INFLATION	0.045845	0.041636	1.101086	0.2765
INTEREST_LEVELS	0.027536	0.002821	9.759502	0.0000
RUPIAH EXCHANGE RATE	0.062120	0.001019	60.94152	0.0000
R-squared	0.600878			
Adjusted R-squared	0.356254			
SE of regression	0.018103	Mean dependent var		1.0000000
Sum squared resid	0.015403	Akaike info criterion		-5.110298
Likelihood logs	134.3126	Schwarz criterion		-4.958782
F-statistics	-15.66667	Hannan Quinn Criter.		-5.052399
Prob(F-statistic)	1.0000000	Durbin-Watson stat		1.702395

Source: Results of processing Eviews 9

Judgment from the consequences of collections processing that has been carried out, the determination 2 as seen from the R-squared is 0. 600878, this expenditure have in mind that the self-governing variables, videlicet inflation, interestingness rates, and the rupiah substitution proportion buoy account for 60. 0% of the drug-addicted changeable or return.so the eternal sleep is explained by over-the-counter variables that are not interested in the model.

4.2 Fixed Effect Model

Table 4.2: Fixed Effect Model Test Results

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.028577	0.010992	2.599792	0.0124
INFLATION	0.045845	0.041636	1.101086	0.2765
INTEREST_LEVELS	0.027536	0.002821	9.759502	0.0000
RUPIAH EXCHANGE RATE	0.062120	0.001019	60.94152	0.0000
R-squared	0.986683	Mean dependent var		1.0000
Adjusted R-squared	0.984575	SD dependent var		0.000000
SE of regression	0.018103	Akaike info criterion		-5.110298
Sum squared resid	0.015403	Schwarz criterion		-4.958782
Likelihood logs	134.3126	Hannan Quinn Criter.		-5.052399
F-statistics	-15.66667	Durbin-Watson stat		1.702395
Prob(F-statistic)	1.0000000			

Source: Results of processing Eviews 9

Judgment from the consequences of the collections processing that has been carried out, the R2 consequences seen from the R-squared are 0. 986683, this expenditure have in mind that the self-governing variables, videlicet inflation, interestingness rates, and the rupiah substitution proportion buoy account for 98. 66% of the drug-addicted changeable or inventory returns. so the eternal sleep is explained by over-the-counter variables that are not interested in the model.

4.3 Random Effect Model

Table 4.3: Random Effect Model Test Results

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	3.559064	2.001276	1.778397	0.0851
INFLATION	-0.779191	0.517784	-1.504858	0.1425
INTEREST_LEVELS	-0.074041	0.061986	-1.194484	0.2413
RUPIAH EXCHANGE RATE	-0.205533	0.127311	-1.614416	0.1166
Effects Specification				
Cross-section fixed (dummy variables)				
R-squared	0.600878	Mean dependent var		0.320196
Adjusted R-squared	0.356254	SD dependent var		0.236131
SE of regression	0.189457	Akaike info criterion		-0.202835
Sum squared resid	1.112712	Schwarz criterion		0.554744
Likelihood logs	25.17228	Hannan Quinn Criter.		0.086659
F-statistics	2.456339	Durbin-Watson stat		3.300599
Prob(F-statistic)	0.012713			

Source: Results of processing Eviews 9

Judgement from the consequences of collections processing that has been carried out; the determination 2 as seen from the R-squared is 0. 600878, this expenditure have in mind that the self-governing variables, videlicet inflation, interestingness rates, and the rupiah substitution proportion buoy account for 60. 08% of the drug-addicted changeable or return. So the eternal sleep is explained by over-the-counter variables that are not interested in the model.

4.4 Selection on the Regression Model

In the venire collections retrogression model, thither are deuce-ace classifications of working model videlicet characteristic chain reaction regression, concentrated chain reaction and serendipitous effect. So it is all-important to evaluation the survival of the representation in progression to accomplish a businesslike estimate. The consequences of the representation survival evaluation are as come after:

a. Chow test

Table 4.4: Chow Test Results

Effects Test	Statistics	df	Prob.
Cross-section F	1.732713	(16.31)	0.0926
Cross-section Chi-square	32.581408	16	0.0084

Source: Results of processing Eviews 9

The expenditure of the Chi-Square apportionment of the consequences obtained victimisationing Eviews 0. 9 are 32. 581408 with a distinct possibility of 0.0084 ($\leq 5\%$) so that it be unsuccessful to eliminate HI, so the representation euphemistic pre-owned is a concentrated chain reaction way of thinking model.

b. Hausman test

Table 4.5: Hausman Test Results

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistics	Chi-Sq. df	Prob.
Cross-section random	6.975465	3	0.0727

Source: Results of processing Eviews 9

The expenditure of the Chi-Square apportionment from computations victimisationing Eviews 9 is 6. 975465 with a distinct possibility of 0. 0727 (less than 5%) so that it be unsuccessful to eliminate HI, so the representation euphemistic pre-owned is a concentrated chain reaction way of thinking model.

4.5 Fixed Effect Model

The procedure of the concentrated chain reaction representation is to approximate the venire collections by victimisationing a cartridge changeable to appropriate the differentiation in intercepts. The delimitation of concentrated chain reaction is supported on the differentiation in the interfere with between individuals on the other hand the interfere with is the corresponding transversely continuance (time intervvariant).

Table 4.6 Test Resultsfixed Effect

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.028577	0.010992	2.599792	0.0124
INFLATION	0.045845	0.041636	1.101086	0.2765
INTEREST_LEVELS	0.027536	0.002821	9.759502	0.0000
RUPIAH EXCHANGE RATE	0.062120	0.001019	60.94152	0.0000
R-squared	0.986683	Mean dependent var		1.0000
Adjusted R-squared	0.984575	SD dependent var		0.000000
SE of regression	0.018103	Akaike info criterion		-5.110298
Sum squared resid	0.015403	Schwarz criterion		-4.958782
Likelihood logs	134.3126	Hannan Quinn Criter.		-5.052399
F-statistics	-15.66667	Durbin-Watson stat		1.702395
Prob(F-statistic)	1.0000000			

Source: Results of processing Eviews 9

Based on the table above, the regression equation model that can be arranged in this study is as follows:

$$\text{Return} = 3.559064 + 0.045845 \text{ Inflation} + 0.027536 \text{ Interest rate} + 0.062120 \text{ Rupiah exchange rate} + e$$

Supported on the in the sky equation, it buoy be seen that the never-ending expenditure is 3. This demonstrates that if inflation, interestingness reprimands and the rupiah substitution proportion chalk up no value, so the appearance testament is never-ending at 3.

4.6 Partial Test (t)

Table 4.7: T. Test Results

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
STOCK RETURNS	0.028577	0.010992	2.599792	0.0124
INFLATION	0.045845	0.041636	1.101086	0.2765
INTEREST_LEVELS	0.027536	0.002821	9.759502	0.0000
RUPIAH EXCHANGE RATE	0.062120	0.001019	60.94152	0.0000

Source: Eviews9 Processing Results

a. Inflation Test

The tcount expenditure of ostentatiousness is 1. 101086 with a significance of 0. 2765, patch the ttable expenditure in this contemplate is calculable by $df = nk \ 51-3 = 48$ with a ttable of 2. 010 with a significance of 0. determination valuetcount(1. 101086) distinct possibility <ttable (2.010) probability value expenditure of 0. 2765 >0. 05 (α) which have in mind that statistically possibility 1 is rejected, signification that ostentatiousness has no chain reaction on inventory turn back in state-owned fellowships on the Indonesia inventory Exchange..

b. Testing of Interest Rates

T count expenditure of interest rate of 9. 759502 with a significance of 0. 0000 patch the ttable expenditure in this contemplate was calculable by $df = nk \ 51-3 = 48$ with a t-table of 2. 010 with a significance of 0. determination valuetcount(9. 759502) >ttable (2010) with a distinct possibility expenditure of 0. 0000 <0. 05 (α) which have in mind that statistically possibility 2 is accepted, signification that interestingness reprimands influence inventory turn back in state-owned fellowships on the Indonesia inventory Exchange.

c. Testing of Rupiah Exchange Rate

T count expenditure of Rupiah substitution rate of 60. 94152 with a significance of 0. 0000 patch the ttable expenditure in this contemplate was calculable by $df = n-51-3 = 48$ with a t-table of 2. 010 with a significance of 0. determination valuetcount(60. 94152) >ttable(1. 67722) with a distinct possibility expenditure of 0. 0000 <0. 05 (α) which have in mind that statistically possibility 3 is accepted, signification that the Rupiah substitution proportion has an chain reaction on inventory turn back in BUMN fellowships on the Indonesia inventory Exchange.

4.7 Simultaneous Test (f)

This F-statistic evaluation is euphemistic pre-owned to influence the significance of the changeable Inflation, interestingness Rate, Rupiah substitution proportion simultaneously if it lay hold of the inventory appearance variable. The F-Statistic expenditure is -15, 66667 and the distinct possibility expenditure is 1. 0000000. F table calculable with df numerator 3 and df denominator $51-3-1=47$ is 2. 80 and for distinct possibility 0.determination value F count (-15. 66667) distinct $<F_{table} (2.80)$ with a expenditure of 1. 0000 $>0. 05 (\alpha)$ which have in mind that possibility 4 is rejected, signification that Inflation, interestingness Rates, Rupiah substitution reprimands chalk up no contemporaneous chain reaction on inventory turn back in BUMN fellowships on the Indonesia inventory Exchange.

4.8 Determination Test

R-square is a coefficient to estimate how the transformation changeable Inflation, interestingness Rate, Rupiah substitution proportion is influenced by the inventory appearance variable. From the concentrated chain reaction retrogression end result the expenditure of the determinative coefficient or R^2 is 0. 986683 or 98.6683 percent. This have in mind that 98. 6683 pct thither is a modification in the inventory appearance changeable which buoy be influenced or explained by the changeable Inflation, interestingness Rates, Rupiah substitution Rates, and the differentiation of 1. 3317 percent% is explained by over-the-counter variables.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of research and discussion in the previous chapter, it can be concluded as follows:

- a. possibility 1 is rejected, which have in mind that ostentatiousness has no chain reaction on inventory turn back in state-owned fellowships on the Indonesia inventory Exchange. possibility 2 is accepted, which have in mind that interestingness reprimands chalk up an chain reaction on inventory turn back in state-owned fellowships on the Indonesia inventory Exchange. possibility 3 is accepted, which have in mind that the rupiah substitution proportion has an chain reaction on inventory turn back in state-owned fellowships on the Indonesia inventory Exchange. possibility 4 is forsook which means Inflation, interestingness reprimands and the rupiah substitution proportion chalk up no contemporaneous chain reaction on inventory returns.
- b. For investors, this evaluation buoy be euphemistic pre-owned as utilitarian enlightenment and buoy furthermore be euphemistic pre-owned as substantial for manufacturing the hold together settlements related their investments.
- c. For companies, it is anticipated to remuneration bounteous consideration to the company's qualification to remuneration consideration to the company's qualification to constitute profits gross (good profits) by manufacturing efficacious and businesslike application of patronage costs, assets property and optimizing the application of existing funds.

- d. For investors should acknowledge the repositioning of the Rupiah substitution proportion and interestingness reprimands thanks to these variables chalk up been proved to chalk up a substantial chain reaction on the company's inventory return. This changeable buoy be euphemistic pre-owned as considerateness for deciding the asset strategy. thanks to the repositioning of the Rupiah substitution proportion and interestingness reprimands testament influence the company's inventory return.

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